

FROM COURTLY LOVE TO CHIVALRIC LOVE: FROM LANCELOT TO DON QUIXOTE, IVANHOE, AND AMADÍS

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Translation of: “*Do amor cortês ao amor cavaleiresco: De Lancelot a Dom Quixote, Ivanhoé e Amadís*”
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ABSTRACT

This article examines the tradition of courtly love in chivalric romances from the 12th century, based on a bibliographical review that includes authors such as Doudet, Raimondo, C.S. Lewis, and Massaud. It concludes that the tradition of courtly love has its roots in *Lancelot ou le Chevalier de la Charrette*, by Chrétien de Troyes, and evolves over time, reflecting the social and cultural transformations of the period, especially under the increasing influence of the Church. In later works, such as *Los cuatro libros del virtuoso caballero Amadís de Gaula*, by Garcí Rodríguez Montalvo, the treatment of love already incorporates the moral and social values of the chivalric romance, demonstrating a significant adaptation to Christian ethics and the sociocultural reality of the 16th century.

Keywords: *Courtly Love. Chivalric romance. Troubador. Arthurian cycle.*

Introduction

This paper examines the medieval tradition of courtly love and its relationship with chivalric love, adopting a literary approach centered on the most representative romances of the time. The study is based on two essential questions: –What are the fundamental characteristics of courtly love in the medieval tradition? – How does courtly love relate to and evolve within chivalric romances throughout history?

In seeking these answers, this study aims not only to outline the distinctive features of courtly love but also to understand its influence on chivalric narratives, revealing how this ideal of love shaped plots and characters, reflecting the social and cultural tensions of the time.

Since the 12th century, courtly love has established itself as a rich and fruitful source of inspiration for various authors, not only in literature but also in cinema. In 1883, the French philologist Gaston Paris (1839-1903) was a pioneer in adopting the term *amour courtois* to describe the concept of Provençal *fin'amor*. Since then, numerous scholars have dedicated

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themselves to studying this literary tradition, exploring its manifestations in different historical periods and literary cycles.

Although often associated with an idealized and platonic form of love, courtly love, as Doudet (2004) emphasizes, could also involve adulterous relationships and sexual consummation. For this reason, it is essential to precisely define the concept of courtly love and investigate how this tradition has been treated in literary works over time.

Within this context, the aim of this study is to examine the representation of courtly love and chivalric love in chivalric romances, with *Lancelot, ou le Chevalier de la Charrette* and *Amadís de Gaula* being the works that best exemplify this tradition.

Methodology

This paper adopts bibliographic research as the primary methodological approach, supported by a thorough analysis of specialized works on the subject. The investigation was conducted through a critical review of the conceptions and interpretations of several renowned authors, such as Boase (1977), C.S. Lewis (1936), Doudet (2004), Massaud (2006), and Raimondo (2013), whose ideas were essential for the construction of the theoretical foundation and the development of the final text.

Development

Courtly love (*amour courtois*) is a concept of romantic relationships that emerged in the 11th century in the region of Poitiers, in Provence, France. During this period, the region was under the rule of William IX of Aquitaine (1071-1127), considered the first troubadour. His granddaughter, Eleanor of Aquitaine, who would later become Queen Consort of both France and England, played a crucial role as a patron of various troubadours, promoting the spread of this new ideal of love. Later, her daughter, Marie de Champagne (Marie de France), continued this tradition by supporting renowned writers such as Chrétien de Troyes, author of *Lancelot, ou le Chevalier de la Charrette*, and Andreas Capellanus, author of *De Amore*.

The original term for courtly love in Provençal was *fin'amor* or *fin'amors*. It was the philologist Gaston Paris who first used the expression *amour courtois* in 1883 in his article

Études sur les romans de la Table Ronde: Lancelot du Lac, II: Le conte de la charrette, published in the journal *Romania* in Paris.

According to Denomy (as cited in RAIMONDO, 2013, p. 44), courtly love is configured as a form of sensual love, but with a fundamental distinction from other manifestations of sexual or conjugal love: its purpose is not the mere satisfaction of physical desires, but rather the personal advancement of the lover, their continuous self-improvement, and the growth of their worth and merit. This ideal of love, therefore, transcends the physical plane, becoming a path to moral and social elevation.

Raimondo (2013, p. 46) also notes that courtly love formed a precise and codified system of etiquette, which became a central element of the aristocratic treatment of love in medieval literature. Within this framework, *amour courtois* emerges not only as a theme of great refinement but also as an ideal of good manners, widely transmitted through chivalric romances and behavior manuals, such as the famous treatise by Andreas Capellanus. In this treatise, *De Amore* (c. 1186), the cleric not only codified the rules of courtly love but also established the social conventions that guided the behavior of lovers in medieval courts. His work thus became a true compendium of amorous wisdom, serving as an essential guide for those who wished to live according to the lofty standards of this idealized love.

According to C. S. Lewis's study (1936, p. 2), the doctrine of *De Amore* can be summarized in four basic principles: humility, courtesy, adultery, and the "religion of love." These principles, which define the essence of courtly love, present a vision of love as not only idealized but also marked by rules and social conventions that shape the behavior of lovers.

Among the various theories regarding the origin of the courtly love tradition, the one proposed by Boase (1997, p. 62) stands out. He suggests that this tradition was imported in the early 12th century from southern France to Muslim Spain. According to this theory, the encounter between Christian and Muslim cultures contributed to the spread and adaptation of the concept of courtly love in different social and cultural contexts.

Furthermore, Raimondo points out that Arabic poetry had a strong influence on this tradition, especially in the literary forms and ideals expressed in medieval courts. Through the cultural exchange between Muslim Spain and Christian courts, many of the themes and codes of behavior that characterize courtly love were amplified and reinterpreted, acquiring new dimensions and meanings:

The consensus is that the system of “courtly love” is for the most part an amalgamation of ideas from troubadours’ songs, Ovidian erotic works, Celtic poems, Christian doctrine, medical treatises, and discussions fashionable in European courtly circles. But in the light of recent studies, the roots of “courtly love”—in its sensual and mystical manifestations—have been traced to Spanish-Arabian poetry. (RAIMONDO, 2013. p.46)

In fact, it was from courtly love that the troubadour lyric and the *cantigas de amor* in Galician-Portuguese emerged, literary forms that became emblematic of medieval culture. During this period, marriages were, for the most part, arrangements made for political or economic reasons, and love between the spouses was not a necessity for the union to be established. Women, in a context of rigid social conventions, rarely had the freedom to choose their husbands, and genuine love between couples was an exception, if it even existed.

Moreover, husbands, often involved in long periods of war, such as during the Crusades, would spend months away from their wives, leaving them isolated and, in a way, "available" for the cult of courtly love. It is within this context of distance and absence that the figure of the wandering knight or troubadour emerges—a character who idealized his lady and felt compelled to perform extraordinary feats—often dangerous and heroic—to prove his worthiness of her love. This love, far from being a mere physical passion, was a constant challenge to the knight's honor and valor, motivating him not only by attraction but by the relentless pursuit of an ideal of virtue and nobility.

Regarding courtly love, many myths and misconceptions have circulated over time. One of the most persistent is the idea that this type of love could never be consummated, and thus, was an exclusively idealized, unattainable, and purely platonic relationship. However, a closer examination of the literature that gave rise to this concept reveals a much more complex and multifaceted picture. Contrary to the commonly spread notion, courtly love was not limited to a spiritual relationship devoid of sensuality. On the contrary, despite its profound idealization, it also carried a strong erotic charge, manifested in a codified manner, within the limits established by the strict etiquette codes of the court.

In various works of medieval literature, it is evident that courtly love, although idealized, was not limited to virtues such as humility, courtesy, and devotion. On the contrary, this type of love also encompassed sensuality and physical desire, which played a fundamental role in the lover’s experience. Thus, the relationship between the knight and his lady was a multidimensional experience that transcended the platonic sphere, simultaneously involving desire, spirituality, and action. Courtly love, therefore, was not reduced to a platonic

fervor but was a complex web of emotions, where the ideal and the real, the emotional and the physical, intertwined.

However, the conception of courtly love underwent a significant transformation in the subsequent novels, especially after the 13th century, as will be explained later. In the main *amour courtois* work of the 12th century, *Lancelot, ou le Chevalier de la Charrette*, the love between Lancelot and Guinevere is forbidden but consummated, always within the conventions of courtly love, which impose secrecy on the intimate relationship.

The following excerpt, taken from the version edited by Bordas (1989), illustrates one of these moments of tension and restrained desire:

4665 *La fenêtre n'est pas bien basse,*
 4666 *Néanmoins Lancelot la franchit*
 4667 *Très rapidement et en toute liberté.*
 4668 *Il trouve Keu dormant dans son lit,*
 4669 *Et ensuite il s'en vint au lit de la reine*
 4670 *Devant lequel il s'incline en adorateur,*
 4671 *Car il ne croit en nulle sainte relique autant qu'il croit en elle.*
 4672 *Et la reine lui tend*
 4673 *Ses bras à sa rencontre, et puis l'enlace*
 4674 *Et l'étreint sur son coeur,*
 4675 *Tout en l'attirant près d'elle dans son lit*
 4676 *Où elle lui fait l'accueil le plus beau*
 4677 *Qu'il lui soit possible de faire,*
 4678 *Car elle y est invitée et par Amour et par son coeur.*
 4679 *Amour la pousse à le recevoir ainsi.*
 4680 *Mais si elle éprouva pour lui un grand amour,*
 4681 *Lui en ressentait pour elle cent mille fois plus,*
 4682 *Car Amour priva tous les autres coeurs*
 4683 *Lorsqu'elle prodigua ses biens au sien;*
 4684 *C'est dans son coeur à lui qu'Amour reprit*
 4685 *Toutes ses forces et déploya toute sa vigueur,*
 4686 *Au point de s'appauvrir dans le coeur des autres.*
 4687 *Maintenant Lancelot possède tout ce qu'il désire,*
 4688 *Puisque la reine accepte avec joie*
 4689 *Sa compagnie et son soulas,*
 4690 *Puisqu'il la tient entre ses bras*
 4691 *Et elle le tient, lui, entre les siens.*
 4692 *Le plaisir qu'il éprouve est à tel point doux et bon*
 4693 *--Plaisir des baisers, des sens--*
 4694 *Qu'il leur advint sans mensonge*
 4695 *Une joie et une merveille*
 4696 *Telles que jamais encore leurs pareilles*
 4697 *Ne furent racontées ni connues;*
 4698 *Mais je maintiendrai toujours le silence le plus parfait*
 4699 *Sur ce qu'on ne doit pas dire dans un conte.*
 4700 *De toutes les joies ce fut la plus exquise*
 4701 *Et la plus délectable*
 4702 *Que l'histoire passe sous silence et garde secrète.*
 4703 *Lancelot fut comblé de joie et de plaisir*
 4704 *Pendant toute cette nuit. (DE TROYES, 1976)*

4665 The window is not very low,
 4666 However, Lancelot crosses it
 4667 Very quickly and with total freedom.
 4668 He finds Keu sleeping in his bed,
 4669 And then he goes to the queen's bed,
 4670 In front of which he bows like a worshiper,
 4671 For he does not believe in any holy relic as much as he believes in her.
 4672 And the queen extends
 4673 Her arms to meet him, and then she wraps
 4674 And presses him to her heart,
 4675 While drawing him close to her in her bed
 4676 Where she gives him the most beautiful reception
 4677 That she is able to give,
 4678 For she is invited by both Love and her heart.
 4679 Love urges her to receive him thus.
 4680 But if she felt great love for him,
 4681 He felt for her a hundred thousand times more,
 4682 For Love deprived all other hearts
 4683 When she lavished her goods upon his;
 4684 It was in her own heart that Love took back
 4685 All its strength and unfolded all its vigor,
 4686 To the point of impoverishing the hearts of others.
 4687 Now Lancelot has everything he desires,
 4688 For the queen joyfully accepts
 4689 His company and his comfort,
 4690 For he has her in his arms
 4691 And she has him, him, in hers.
 4692 The pleasure he feels is so sweet and good
 4693 --Pleasure of kisses, of the senses--
 4694 That they experienced without deceit
 4695 A joy and a wonder
 4696 Such that never before have their like
 4697 Been told or known;
 4698 But I will always keep the most perfect silence
 4699 About what should not be said in a tale.
 4700 Of all joys, this was the most exquisite
 4701 And the most delightful
 4702 That the story silences and keeps secret.
 4703 Lancelot was filled with joy and pleasure
 4704 Throughout that entire night. (*Translation ours*)

In this passage, Lancelot crosses the window with great speed and freedom, symbolizing the transgression of social and chivalric norms to meet Guinevere. She welcomes him, and he "was filled with joy and pleasure throughout that entire night" (verses 4703 and 4704). The action, though physical, remains within the context of idealized and distant love, reflecting the knight's dilemma between his duties and his passion. This conflict, present in many medieval narratives, reveals the tension between true love and the constraints of reality.

With the growing power of the Church from the 13th century onwards, the concept of courtly love underwent a significant transformation, increasingly turning toward the spiritualization of its principles, moving away from the physical dimension of desire. Under the influence of Christian morality, the knight began to idealize his lady as an object of spiritual worship, associating her with the values of purity and virtue that predominated in Catholic doctrine. This reinterpretation of courtly love resulted in a fundamental shift: the romantic relationship ceased to be viewed as a pursuit of physical satisfaction and came to be seen as a path of moral elevation, where the knight saw himself, to some extent, in a process of purification and spiritual refinement.

In the 16th century, a period that marks the height of chivalric romances written in Castilian, the work *Amadís de Gaula* stands out as an example of how chivalric love was shaped by the influence of both spirituality and Christian morality. The language used in this work reflects an approach to love that, while maintaining immersion in chivalric values, presents a representation of the intimacy between the protagonists in a subtle and indirect manner, imbued with a more spiritual and religious aura, distinct from the one that prevailed in earlier romances. In this new context, chivalric love combines, in a harmonious way, spirituality with physical consummation, but always within a framework of Christian and chivalric values, which makes this vision of love distinguish itself from both the more puritanical traditional courtly love and the romantic love that would emerge in later periods.

This transformation can be observed when comparing the relationship between Amadís and Oriana with the love between Lancelot and Guinevere, as presented in the Arthurian romances. While the love between Lancelot and Guinevere is marked by transgression and a forbidden nature, reflecting the tension between desire and duty, the love between Amadís and Oriana, in contrast, is free from any moral restrictions, being blessed by the institution of marriage. This difference between the romantic relationships is particularly revealing of the evolution of the concept of love within the context of chivalric romances, where spirituality begins to intertwine increasingly with the conception of idealized harmony and union. This process culminates, in the case of Amadís and Oriana's relationship, in a union that not only transcends earthly desires but is also legitimized and celebrated by society and the Church, reflecting the pursuit of moral and social legitimacy that reinforces the Christian principles of the time. The transformation of love, from an initially transgressive passion to a relationship of purity and religious approval, exemplifies the transition from medieval conceptions to the more refined ideologies of chivalric romances.

A clear example of this shift can be found in the following passage from the work *Amadís de Gaula*, where the relationship between the protagonists is described in a manner that reflects this new conception of love, one that is more spiritual and legitimized:

[...] *llegó a la cámara de Oriana, su señora, que lo atendía con otro tan leal y verdadero amor como el que consigo llevaba, así que con muchos besos y abrazos fueron juntos, sin haber envidia a ningunos, que verdaderamente en el mundo se amasen, considerando no haber en el suyo par, acostados en su lecho.* (GARCÍ, 2022. p. 564)

([...] He arrived at the chamber of Oriana, his lady, who treated him with as loyal and true a love as the one he carried with him, so that with many kisses and embraces they were together, without envy of anyone, truly in the world, considering that there was no equal to them in their own, lying in their bed, translation ours).

In the context of Romanticism, the concept of courtly love reemerged with a renewed emphasis on emotional intensity, suffering, and desire, now more visceral. However, this love was often accompanied by frustration and tragedy, elements that came to dominate the romantic representations of the era. In the 19th century, Sir Walter Scott reinterpreted the tradition of courtly love in light of Romanticism in his work *Ivanhoe* (1819), setting the narrative in the 12th century, during the period of wars between Saxons and Normans, shortly after the Norman conquest of England. In the work, the love stories between Ivanhoe and Rowena, or between Ivanhoe and Rebecca, are marked by an emotional intensity characteristic of Romanticism, reflecting the transformation of courtly love into a more dramatic and conflicted ideal.

Returning to the *amour courtois* of the early days, among the key representatives of courtly troubadourism, notable names include Jaufré Rudel, Bernard de Ventadour, Thibaut de Champagne, La Châtelaine de Vergy, Guillem de Cabestanh, Marie de France, Andreas Capellanus, and especially Chrétien de Troyes. His romance *Lancelot* became a cornerstone in the construction of the courtly love tradition, laying the foundations for the representation of love that is both idealized and, simultaneously, erotic, which permeates medieval narratives.

By idealizing love as both a spiritual and physical force, Chrétien de Troyes played a fundamental role in shaping a conception of love that, while reverent and devoted, also incorporated an erotic and emotional charge. This duality between spiritual idealism and physical attraction would become a key element in the works of chivalric romance, being

developed and refined over the following centuries. From this perspective, courtly love, as conceived by Chrétien, was not limited to a mere platonic or devotional love; it also involved an emotional depth that was both idealized and, in certain contexts, erotic.

Regarding the characteristics that define courtly love, it is well known that it should meet a series of fundamental requirements, which, according to Doudet (2004, p. 7-8), can be summarized as follows:

- The lady should be married or engaged and have a higher social status than the suitor.
- The lady's husband should not be aware of the romantic relationship.
- There was a relationship of submission from the knight to the lady, who could demand anything from him, and he could not refuse.
- The relationship went through several phases and, on some occasions, could culminate in sexual consummation.

On the other hand, Andreas Capellanus in his treatise *De Amore* (circa 1185), at the request of Marie de Champagne, daughter of King Louis VII of France and Aliénor d'Aquitaine, presented a systematization of the rules governing courtly love. In the treatise, the author formulates 31 rules that meticulously detail the behaviors and attitudes expected of a love-stricken knight. Additionally, Capellanus makes an important distinction between two types of love: *amor purus* and *amor mixtus*. The *amor purus*, characterized by purity and the idealization of romantic love, differs from *amor mixtus*, which includes the "supreme reward," associated with physical consummation.

Capellanus also establishes an important distinction between two types of lovers: the *sapiens et ingeniosus amator* and the *simplex amator*. The first, the wise and ingenious lover, is expected to possess wisdom and refinement, moderating his desires discreetly and keeping his feelings secret, in accordance with the values of the medieval court. The *simplex amator*, on the other hand, is one whose impulsive nature prevents him from maintaining the necessary reserve, being unable to control or hide his desires. This dichotomy reflects the central tension of courtly love, which requires both virtue and self-control, as well as the acknowledgment of human passion in its most pure and genuine form.

In addition, it is important to highlight that Countess Marie de Champagne, one of the most prominent figures in the medieval court of love, sponsored a court of love where conflicts between lovers were judged according to the principles of the courtly love code. In

Chapter VII of Book II, Capellanus presents as many as twenty-one judgments of love (Capellanus, p. 233), resolved by various noblewomen, including the Countess of Champagne, Queen Aliénor, and Lady Emengarda of Narbonne. The resolutions of these love conflicts, often based on the tenets of *amour courtois*, not only reinforced values of devotion and loyalty, but also emphasized the active role of women as mediators in romantic relationships, a symbolic power that reflected their influence in the social and cultural structures of the time.

Courtly love was structured in various levels or stages, ranging from the first glance of the knight at the lady to the full consummation of the romantic relationship. This progression, which involved a series of courting steps, challenges, and trials, was widely reflected in medieval literary works, where love was depicted as a gradual process of emotional and spiritual development. A notable example of this structure can be found in the work *Flamenca*, an anonymous romance written in *langue d'oc* (circa 1240), which illustrates this knight's journey in great detail. In the narrative, love evolves from a platonic admiration, characterized by an idealized devotion to the lady, to the consummation of desire, always guided by a strict code of honor, devotion, and sacrifice. The work reveals how, within the context of courtly love, each stage of the romantic relationship required the knight not only courage and skill but also an incessant pursuit of moral and spiritual refinement, which was directly reflected in his actions and decisions (Doudet, 2004, p. 30-37).

At the beginning of the relationship, the knight was referred to as *soupirant* (the "sighing" one), marking the initial phase of admiration, characterized by desire and the idealized contemplation of the lady. As the courtship progressed, the knight reached the second level, known as *suppliant* (the "supplicant"), in which he began indirect contact with the lady, often through love messages sent by intermediaries. This stage was crucial to establish the romantic bond, as the knight, by taking the initiative, would submit to a series of courtly norms and rituals. If the lady accepted the courtship, the knight would then demonstrate his love in a more tangible way, showing his dedication through acts of valor, such as participating in jousting tournaments, where he would put himself to the test to earn the approval of his beloved.

If the knight were accepted as a lover, he would reach the pinnacle of courtship, known as *drut*, which represented the peak of the romantic relationship. This moment often culminated in the physical consummation of love, which sealed the bond between the two.

However, when the lady rejected the knight, this setback could provoke in him a deep feeling of anger and contempt, often resulting in a transformation of his behavior. The knight, in his frustration, would adopt the figure of the *profaçador*, characterized by bitterness and the public expression of his disappointment. In the Galician-Portuguese context, this type of reaction manifested in *cantigas de maldizer* (songs of cursing), in which the knight lyrically expressed his indignation and resentment over the rejection, using poetry as a means to externalize his emotions and publicly attack the lady who had spurned him.

Finally, the courtly relationship had to be conducted with the utmost secrecy and discretion. In poems and letters, the enamored knight, as part of the conventions of courtship, avoided revealing the real name of his beloved. Instead, he used a *senhal* or pseudonym, a device that preserved the aura of mystery and idealized distance, which were essential characteristics that defined courtly love. This practice of concealment not only reinforced the platonic and spiritual nature of the relationship but also ensured that the knight remained in a submissive and reverent position, never overstepping the boundaries imposed by society and the code of honor.

To review the treatment of courtly love in chivalric romances, one can refer to the classification of the main literary cycles proposed by Massaud Moisés (2006, p. 38), which organizes these romances into three major groups:

- The Classical cycle, which draws inspiration from Greco-Latin themes;
- The Carolingian cycle, featuring Charlemagne and the Twelve Peers of France;
- The Breton or Arthurian cycle, centered on King Arthur and the Knights of the Round Table.

In the context of the Arthurian cycle, chivalric romances begin to recount the adventures of their heroes, deeply immersed in the tradition of courtly love, where knights undertake their feats driven by devotion and love for their ladies. In this setting, Raimondo (2013, p. 42) notes that, before Chrétien de Troyes, the focus of the narratives was predominantly on the knights' warlike exploits and the glorification of their homelands, with female figures, when mentioned, assuming a secondary and often symbolic role. However, it was Chrétien de Troyes who, with his famous romance about Lancelot, definitively inaugurated the incorporation of courtly love into the Arthurian cycle, positioning King Arthur's court as a stage for the intertwined amorous and heroic dilemmas.

From the 12th century onwards, at the court of Marie de Champagne and under the influence of authors such as Bernart de Ventadorn and Chrétien de Troyes, courtly love became a central theme in European literature, undergoing a gradual evolution in its treatment until it eventually gave rise, centuries later, to the concept of chivalric love. Following this, the principal chivalric romances will be presented, including the parody of these romances in the work *El Ingenioso Hidalgo Don Quijote de La Mancha* (Mongelli et al., 2012, p. 285-288).

- *Lancelot ou le Chevalier de la charrette*: (1177-1181), Chrétien de Troyes;
- *Amadís de Gaula* (c. 1496-1508), Garcí Rodríguez Montalvo;
- *Baladro del Sabio Merlin* (1498);
- *Oliveros de Castilla* (1499);
- *Tristán de Leonis* (1501);
- *Las Sergas de Esplandián* (1510-1521), Garcí Rodríguez Montalvo;
- *Tirante el Blanc* (1511);
- *Palmerín de Oliva* (1511), Francisco Vásquez;
- *Tristán el Joven* (1534);
- *Palmerín de Inglaterra, Libro I* (1547);
- *Palmerín de Inglaterra, Libro II* (1548);
- *Don Quijote de la Mancha, I Parte* (1605), Miguel de Cervantes;
- *Don Quijote de la Mancha, II Parte* (1614), Alfonso Fernández de Avellaneda;
- *Don Quijote de la Mancha, II Parte* (1615), Miguel de Cervantes.

Although *El Ingenioso Hidalgo Don Quijote de la Mancha* is mentioned to establish a chronological reference, it is important to emphasize that the work should not be confused with a chivalric romance. In fact, *Don Quixote* is a parody of these romances, challenging the popular imagination that often associates it with this tradition (Musse, 2012). Additionally, Vieira, as cited in Schechner (2015, p. 66), notes that *Don Quixote* was initially considered a comedic book, being viewed as "the work that destroyed an old genre [...] burlesquely lowering the seriousness of knight-errantry.

"*Los cuatro libros del virtuoso caballero Amadís de Gaula*, a work by Garcí Rodríguez Montalvo, is widely recognized as the masterpiece of chivalric romances in Castilian language. This novel, with its complexity and depth, plays a crucial role in understanding the parody of courtly love that Cervantes constructs in *Don Quixote*.

Indeed, the *Caballero de la Triste Figura* makes several references to *Amadís de Gaula*, whose extraordinary feats and ideals of chivalry he not only admires but attempts to imitate, believing himself worthy of replicating such heroics and the high code of honor that characterize the original romance.

With *Amadís de Gaula*, the Arthurian courtly tradition is not only continued but also transformed, as the tone of the prose is subtly modified to align with the values and social norms of 16th-century Spanish society, as well as the strict moral parameters imposed by the Church. This adaptation reflects the attempt to reconcile the ideals of chivalry and courtly love with the expectations of an era deeply influenced by Christian morality and the established social order (Raimondo, 2013, p. 49).

The presentation of the love topic in Amadís is, in general, similar in psychology, rhetorical devices, plot situations, and literary sources to the exposition given the same matter in the Arthurian romances of Chrétien de Troyes but it differs in moral tone, ethical evaluation, and intent.

Thus, by secretly marrying, Amadís and Oriana do not merely become lovers, as was common in the Arthurian cycle chivalric romances, but assume the position of spouses, giving their relationship a depth and seriousness that distinguish it. In fact, the chivalric romances of this period, far from being read merely as "books of exploits," came to be interpreted primarily as true treatises on love, where emotions and emotional bonds become the center of the narrative, overshadowing heroic adventures and military feats.

The adventures of the heroic knights, which once stood out for their military feats and extraordinary accomplishments, became subordinated to the theme of love, a transformation evident in the work *Amadís de Gaula*. In this context, Amadís' great deeds, far from being motivated solely by a desire for honor or glory, are driven by his deep love for Oriana.

As Menéndez y Pelayo observes as cited by Raimondo (2013, p. 42), "Love, which in the heroic songs had no importance at all, became the main motive for the actions of the heroes." This shift in focus, which places love at the center of heroic actions, is a clear reflection of a new literary approach that subordinates war and conquests to a romantic and emotional ideal.

Additionally, O'Connor as cited by Raimondo (2013, p. 42) supported this perspective, stating that, in his time, *Amadís de Gaula* was predominantly read as a true treatise on love, surpassing its classification as a mere traditional chivalric romance.

Love and his lady occupy almost as much of the hero's attention as fighting and there is little doubt that in the sixteenth century Amadís de Gaula was read principally as a book of love." In fact, he says, "ladies provide the incentive for many a battle and are often the cause of war.

The Spanish philologist Menéndez y Pelayo summarizes the profile of *Amadís de Gaula* as the perfect knight and hero, according to the mentality of the time:

El ideal de la Tabla Redonda aparece refinado, purificado y ennoblecido. Sin el vértigo amoroso de Tristán, sin la adultera pasión de Lanzarote, sin el equívoco misticismo de los héroes del Santo Grial, Amadís es el tipo del perfecto caballero, el espejo del valor y de la cortesía, el dechado de vasallos leales y de finos y constantes amadores, el escudo y amparo de los débiles y menesterosos, el brazo armado puesto al servicio del orden moral y de la justicia. (Menéndez y Pelayo as cited in RAIMONDO, p. 65)

(The ideal of the Round Table appears refined, purified, and ennobled. Without the amorous vertigo of Tristan, without the adulterous passion of Lancelot, without the ambiguous mysticism of the heroes of the Holy Grail, Amadís is the type of the perfect knight, the mirror of valor and courtesy, the model of loyal vassals and fine and constant lovers, the shield and protector of the weak and needy, the armed arm put at the service of moral order and justice, translation ours).

Ultimately, as mentioned earlier, it is crucial not to confuse the novel *El Ingenioso Hidalgo Don Quijote de la Mancha* with a typical chivalric romance, as this work actually functions as a parody of traditional chivalric novels. In this sense, in addition to immersing himself in the reading of numerous books of chivalry, the nobleman Don Quixote makes continuous references throughout his journey to the wandering knights who preceded him, whom he admires and is inspired by.

Conclusion

The main objective of this paper was to analyze the tradition of courtly love and chivalric love based on the most representative works, such as *Lancelot ou le Chevalier de la Charrette* and *Amadís de Gaula*. Initially, the concept of this medieval tradition, its origin, central characteristics, and evolution were presented.

In light of the considerations presented, it can be concluded that the tradition of courtly love has its roots in the 12th century, in the French Provence, beginning to manifest in the chivalric romances, especially in Chrétien de Troyes' *Lancelot ou le Chevalier de la*

Charrette. In this context, it was observed that courtly love solidified as a central theme in various chivalric romances in the following centuries, reaching its masterpiece in *Los cuatro libros del virtuoso caballero Amadís de Gaula* in the 16th century.

It was also found that, over time, the literary treatment of courtly love adapted to new historical and cultural realities, especially under the influence of the Church, which sought to guide the morality of individuals. Romantic works such as *Ivanhoe* by Sir Walter Scott, in the 19th century, although inspired by courtly love, distanced themselves from its original conception, reflecting the changes in values and social expectations of the time.

To conclude, it was analyzed that the novel *El Ingenioso Hidalgo Don Quijote de la Mancha* by Miguel de Cervantes should be understood not only as a parody of the chivalric romances but also of the courtly love tradition itself. Through the figure of Don Quixote, Cervantes not only satirizes chivalric ideals but also offers a profound critique of social conventions and the exaggerated idealization of love in medieval narratives, providing a critical reflection on the values of his time.

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